

Inhibition of *S. oryzae* by *B. zeicola*. 1 = *Sarocladium oryzae*, 2 = *Bipolaris zeicola*, 3 = upper colony - *B. zeicola*, lower colony - *S. oryzae*.

S. oryzae in vitro (see figure). A clear inhibition zone was formed between the pathogen and the antagonist. The undiluted culture filtrate of *B. zeicola*

tested on *S. oryzae* completely inhibited mycelial growth of the pathogen. The isolate did not inhibit *P. oryzae* and *H. oryzae*. □

Toxicity of essential oils against *Rhizoctonia solani* Kühn fungus causing sheath blight (ShB) in rice

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We isolated essential oils of *Citrus sinensis*, *Eucalyptus globulus*, *Ocimum*

canum, and *Pinus roxburghii* by hydro-distillation through Clevenger's apparatus and tested their toxicity to *R. solani*, using the classical poisoned food technique.

Because these oils were insoluble in water, desired concentrations were prepared by mixing the requisite amount in 0.5 ml acetone, then mixing that with 14.5 ml sterilized molten PDA medium cooled to 40 °C, in a

sterilized petri plate. Control sets were established by mixing sterilized distilled water in 0.5 ml acetone. All plates were inoculated with a single mycelial disc (5 mm diam) of *R. solani*.

For mycelial dry weight yield, a single mycelial disc of actively growing *R. solani* 5 mm diam was transferred to 100 ml autoclaved and cooled liquid Czapek-Dox + 0.05% yeast extract supplemented with enough of each oil dissolved in 0.5 ml of acetone to get the needed concentration. Medium without oil was the control.

Plates were kept at 26 ± 1 °C. Observations were made after 4 d (radial growth) and 15 d (mycelial dry weight yield).

Growth of the test pathogen was completely inhibited by *O. canum* oil at 0.2% concentration. Oil of *C. sinensis* at the same concentration reduced growth by 87%; oil of *P. roxburghii* by 75.0% (see table).

Mycelial dry weight yield was reduced markedly by oil of *C. sinensis* (to 32 mg compared to 214.0 mg for control).

The inhibitory effects of these oils may be attributed to the presence of some antifungal ingredients in the oil. Several antifungal properties of higher plants, in the form of volatile or nonvolatile compounds, have already been demonstrated against *Aspergillus* sp., *Fusarium* sp., *Macrophomina phaseolina*, and *Sclerotium rolfsii*. Natural products, such as protoanemonin, allamandoside, and essential oils of *O. canum*, also have been known to be more effective than synthetic fungicides. The products of higher plants that have shown antifungal activity may be useful to control ShB in rice. □

Toxicity of essential oils to *Rhizoctonia solani*.

Plant oil	Concentration (%)	Growth inhibition ^a (%)	Mycelial dry wt yield ^b (mg)	Sclerotia production ^b (% reduction)
<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	0.05	47.8	134.5 ± 2.65	61.2 ± 2.04
	0.10	54.5	124.1 ± 2.53	13.7 ± 3.38
	0.15	76.1	60.6 ± 2.78	89.1 ± 4.22
	0.20	87.0	32.0 ± 2.09	92.6 ± 3.86
<i>Eucalyptus globulus</i>	0.05	28.3	182.6 ± 2.44	56.4 ± 3.91
	0.10	47.5	126.3 ± 2.89	69.5 ± 3.59
	0.15	53.9	112.1 ± 2.77	76.2 ± 2.14
	0.20	59.2	89.3 ± 1.91	81.0 ± 1.46
<i>Ocimum canum</i>	0.05	53.2	105.0 ± 2.72	74.0 ± 2.19
	0.10	64.8	92.3 ± 3.18	87.5 ± 1.45
	0.15	91.1	25.3 ± 1.96	96.0 ± 1.26
	0.20	100	0	0
<i>Pinus roxburghii</i>	0.05	35.2	157.3 ± 2.94	49.6 ± 3.69
	0.10	47.8	125.6 ± 2.12	57.0 ± 2.52
	0.15	52.6	114.6 ± 2.88	65.7 ± 1.94
	0.20	75.0	62.6 ± 2.44	84.6 ± 1.29
Control	—	—	214.0 ± 2.94	—

^aEach figure represents the average of 3 determinations. ^bEach value is the mean of 3 replications, ± standard error. All oils tested were toxic at higher concentrations. *Ocimum canum* at 0.20% concentration completely inhibited mycelial growth.

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